

Studies on the Coagulation of Antimony and Gold Sols by Light Extinction and Surface Leaving Techniques

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Antimony and gold sols have been prepared and their precipitation values studied by KCl, BaCl₂, and AlCl₃ by employing the light extinction and the surface leaving methods in the light of the equation

$$C = a + \frac{m \cdot 1/t}{n + 1/t}$$

On adding different concentrations of these electrolytes to the sol the corresponding times of coagulation have been determined by light extinction and visual surface leaving method. The times of coagulation by both the methods could not be expected to be identical, because the stage of coagulation may not be the same, when different techniques are employed. The merit of this equation, however, is not affected, in as much as the relation between $1/C - a$ of the electrolyte and their respective times of coagulation has been found to be linear. The constants a , m , and n have been determined for each electrolyte.

Extensive studies on coagulation have been carried out earlier by many workers.^{1,8} In spite of their extensive work the fact remains that no suitable expression is found in the literature which may correlate the concentration of the electrolyte with the time of slow coagulation.

Mathews and Murphy⁹, Dumanski and Scherschnev¹⁰ while investigating the relation between the electrolyte concentration and the stability of sols, have brought forward the important fact that time of coagulation is a function of the electrolyte concentration which, as expressed by Dumanski, was of the form $t = ac^n$, where t is the time of coagulation and C is the number of ml. of the electrolyte added, a and n being constants for the given system. Mathews and Murphy⁹ further found that for every electrolyte there was a limiting concentration below which coagulation was not possible.

Bhattacharya and coworkers¹¹ made an interesting study of the relation between the concentration of the electrolyte and time of coagulation. They plotted the concentration of the electrolyte, C , with the reciprocal of the corresponding time of coagulation, $1/t$, using arsenious sulphide, chromium hydroxides, ferric hydroxide, copper ferrocyanide,

1. Smoluchowski *Z. physikal Chem.*, 1917, **92**, 129.
2. Freundlich, *Kolloid, Z.*, **23**, 163, .
3. Zsigmondy, *Z. physikal Chem.*, 1918, **92**, 600.
4. Weiser, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, **25**, 399.
5. *Arktio Kemi, Mineral. Geol.*, **7**, No. 6, 1918.
6. Krnyt and Van Arkel, *Rec. trav. Chim.* 1920, **39**, 656; **40**, 169.
7. Dhar and Ghosh, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, **30**, 294. Mukherjee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **115**, 461.
8. Joshi, *this Journal.*, 1933, **10**, 326; 1934, **11**, 133.
9. *Science*, 1921, **43**, 581.
10. *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **62**, 187.
11. *This Journal*, 1951, **28**, 179, 638; 1952, **29**, 687, 759; *Kolloid Z.*, 1955, **141**, 95; *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India-24th Annual Session*, 1954.

and prussian blue sols and obtained hyperbolic curves in the majority of cases. They suggested empirically the new equation

$$C = a + \frac{m \cdot 1/t}{n + 1/t} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where a , m , and n are constants. The constant ' a ' is determined graphically by plotting C against $1/t$, and then the plot of $1/(C-a)$ and ' t ' is found to be linear.

Recently Ghosh¹² discussed the kinetics of coagulation in the light of Smoluchowski's equation and also the theory of stability of lyophobic colloids in terms of the energy of repulsion V_R and the stability ratio W which increases with the particle radius r . He further assumed with plausible reasons that the ϵ factor in the Smoluchowski's equation for slow coagulation was proportional to $1/W$ or $1/r$. He deduced by approximation that ϵ and the time of coagulation can be represented by the equation,

$$\epsilon = \frac{K}{1 + at}$$

where K includes n_0 (initial no. of particles per ml) and the proportionality constant, and a represents in Smoluchowski's equation, where α is constant.

In a later communication Ghosh and Gangopadhyay¹³ deduced Bhattacharya's equation,

$$1/C - a = \frac{n}{m} t + \frac{1}{m}$$

from the Reerink's equation for a given colloid and electrolyte which was expressed as

$$\log W = -(\alpha + i) \log C - \log K,$$

where K stood for all the constant terms in the expression worked out by Verwey and Overbeek¹⁴ the plot of $\log W$ against $\log C$ was shown by Reerink to be linear. Similarly the plot of $1/C - a$ and t is found to be linear according to Bhattacharya's equation. Since Reerink's equation¹⁴ has got a theoretical basis, Ghosh justified the validity of Bhattacharya's equation on theoretical grounds.

In this paper we communicate our observations on the slow coagulation of antimony sulphide and gold sols by the light extinction and surface leaving methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

The antimony sulphide sol was prepared by passing slow bubbles of H_2S into a little distilled water in which a solution of potassium antimony tartrate was dropped from a burette. Excess of H_2S was removed by passing a current of purified hydrogen. The sol was then carefully dialysed in a parchment paper bag.

12. *This Journal*, 1958, 35, 671.

13. *Ibid.*, 1959, 36, 811.

14. "Theory of Stability of Lyophobic Colloids" pp. 167-78; *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1954; "Colloid Science", vol II, 1952, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1954.

Gold sol was prepared by heating 120 to 150 ml. of distilled water in a 300 ml. beaker, 1% of gold chloride solution (1 ml) was added and then $M/5$ solution of extra pure potassium carbonate (2.5-3 ml). As soon as the solution came near boiling, it was stirred and 2 to 3 ml of dilute formaldehyde solution (1 ml of commercial 40% formalin to 100 ml water) was added quickly and the mixture was removed from the burner. Reduction was complete in about a minute. The resulting sol was ruby-red and transparent to light. It was then dialysed in a parchment paper bag.

The time of coagulation was determined by carefully noting the time at which the separation of the clear liquid took place at the surface. Five cleaned dried test tubes, each containing v ml of the electrolyte and $(5-v)$ ml of water, and 5 ml of sol were allowed

FIG. 1

time in mins.

FIG. 2

to stand undisturbed. The time at which the coagulation just began to leave the surface of the liquid was noted very carefully. The mean of the readings for the five test tubes was taken as the time of coagulation corresponding to v ml of the electrolyte.

The apparatus used for determining the time of coagulation by light extinction method was an Eel photoelectric colorimeter which consisted of a photoelectric cell which received a constant incident radiation from a two volt bulb. The pointer of the apparatus was adjusted by taking distilled water in the tube to zero of the scale with the help of a screw attached in it. A mixture of water, electrolyte, and sol was taken in the same tube and light extinction was noted with time. The time of maximum extinction was taken as the time of coagulation.

TABLE I

Slow coagulation with M/4. KCl.
Conc. of Sb_2S_3 sol = 0.096g./litre

Ppt. conc. (C) of KCl.	Coagulation time (t) (t) for max ext.	1/t.	a.	1/(C-a).
A. Visual method.				
65.5 mM	12.5 min.	0.080		0.043
64.2	15.4	0.065		0.046
61.5	20.0	0.050	42.5 mM	0.053
59.0	25.0	0.040		0.061
56.0	33.3	0.030		0.074
52.0	50.0	0.020		0.105
B. Light extinction method.				
65.0 mM	0.50 min	2.00		0.044
62.5	1.00	1.00		0.0500
60.0	4.00	0.25	42.5 mM	0.0571
57.5	6.00	0.16		0.0666
55.0	16.00	0.062		0.0800
52.5	25.00	0.040		0.1000

TABLE II

Slow coagulation with M/100-BaCl₂.
Conc. of Sb_2S_3 sol same as in Table I;

C of BaCl ₂ .	t for max. ext.	1/t.	a.	1/(C-a).
A. Visual method				
1.69 mM	9.1 min.	0.11		1.45
1.67	10.0	0.10		1.50
1.65	11.1	0.09		1.54
1.62	12.5	0.08		1.61
1.59	14.3	0.07	1.0 mM	1.70
1.51	20.0	0.05		1.96
1.42	28.5	0.035		2.40
1.35	40.0	0.025		2.84
B. Light extinction method.				
1.80	0.50	2.000		1.250
1.70	1.50	0.65		1.428
1.60	3.00	0.33	1.00	1.666
1.50	5.00	0.182		2.000

TABLE III

Slow coagulation with M/3000. AlCl₃.
 Conc. of Sb₂S₃ sol same as in Table I.

<i>C</i> of AlCl ₃ .	Time <i>t</i> for max. ext.	1/ <i>t</i> .	<i>a</i>	1/(<i>C-a</i>).
		A. Visual Method.		
0.0475 mM	16.6 min	0.06		
0.0470	18.2	0.055		44.4
0.0455	25.0	0.040	0.025 mM	45.4
0.0445	28.5	0.035		48.8
0.0417	40.0	0.025		51.3
				59.5
		B. Light extinction method.		
0.0500	5	0.20		40.000
0.0443	9	0.11		45.662
0.0420	13	0.077	0.0223	51.813
0.0407	21	0.048		63.694
0.0376	32	0.031		79.365

TABLE IV

Slow coagulation with M/10-KCl.
 Conc. of gold sol=0.038 g./litre.

<i>C</i> of KCl.	<i>t</i> for max ext.	1/ <i>t</i> .	<i>a</i>	1/(<i>C-a</i>)
		A. Visual Method		
29.5 mM	7.1 min	0.140		0.142
28.5	12.0	0.084		0.166
27.5	18.2	0.055		0.200
26.5	28.5	0.035	22.50 mM	0.250
25.5	47.6	0.021		0.333
		B. Light extinction method.		
28.50	5.50	0.181		0.166
27.50	10.00	0.100	22.50	2.200
26.50	16.60	0.06		0.250
25.50	28.60	0.035		0.333

TABLE V

Slow coagulation with M/400 BaCl₂.
 Conc. of gold sol same as in Table IV.

<i>C</i> of BaCl ₂ .	for max ext.	1/ <i>t</i> .	<i>a</i> .	1/(<i>C-a</i>).
		A. Visual Method		
0.9625 mM	13.0 min.	0.077		6.600
0.9325	22.2	0.045		8.000
0.9125	35.7	0.028	0.8125 mM	10.000
0.8875	59.0	0.017		13.300
0.8625	71.4	0.014		
		B. Light extinction method.		
0.9625	2.2	0.445		6.66
0.9325	4.1	0.245		8.00
0.9125	7.1	0.140	0.8125	10.00
0.8875	11.8	0.085		13.33
0.8625	20.0	0.050		20.00
0.8500	28.6	0.035		26.70

TABLE VI

Slow coagulation with $M/3000\text{-AlCl}_3$.
Conc of gold sol same as in Table IV.

C of AlCl_3 .	t for max. ext.	$1/t$	α	$1/(C-\alpha)$.
A. Visual method.				
0.0577 mM	17.7	0.057	0.0337 mM	41.70
0.0560	22.5	0.044		43.10
0.0554	33.3	0.030		46.00
0.0539	50.0	0.020		50.00
0.0515	77.0	0.130		56.18
0.0500	100.0	0.010		61.35
B. Light extinction method.				
0.0648	1.25	0.800	0.034	32.50
0.0640	1.60	0.625		33.3
0.0609	3.45	0.290		37.00
0.0578	6.06	0.165		41.7
0.0547	9.10	0.110		47.5

TABLE VII

Values of parametric constants.

	Sb_2S_3 Sol.			Au sol		
	KCl	BaCl_2	AlCl_3	KCl	BaCl_2	AlCl_3
α	42.5 (42.5)	1.0 (1.0)	0.025 (0.022)	22.5 (22.5)	0.8125 (0.8125)	0.0337 (0.034)
m	40 (22.7)	1 (0.83)	0.028 (0.030)	9.00 (7.8)	0.2 (0.2)	0.027 (0.032)
n	20.0 (43.13)	1.2 (3.32)	0.038 (0.018)	10.90 (13.26)	0.07 (0.30)	0.007 (0.072)

Note:—Values within parenthesis have been determined by light extinction method.

DISCUSSION

The parametric constants α , m , and n are constants in equation (I). These have been interpreted in our previous communication where ' α ' has been defined as the critical stability concentration of the electrolyte for the sol by which the coagulation does not take place in a measurable time. ' m ' is that concentration of the electrolyte which is required for immediate coagulation of the sol and n is a constant which has the dimensions of $1/t$. The physical significance of n is difficult, but assuming the foregoing dimensions of n it seems to represent the sensitivity or susceptibility of the sol to the electrolyte which, *a priori*, should depend on such factors as frequency of collisions, thickness of double layer, charge neutralisation, and ζ -potential and the surface properties also such as adsorption and interfacial tension.

The value of the constant a may be derived theoretically when $1/t=0$, i. e., when t is infinitely large in which case $1/t$ can be neglected with respect to n . This theoretical reasoning to interpret a receives support by the fact that the lyophobic colloid can assimilate very small concentration of electrolytes without coagulating within a measurable time. It is under such condition that $1/t$ can be neglected with respect to 'n'. According to the treatment of Ghosh¹² $n=1/T$, where T is the time for rapid coagulation. Since the time for slow coagulation ' t ' will always be much greater than T , $1/T$ or n will be very much greater than $1/t$. Therefore $1/t$ can be neglected with respect to 'n' when it is very small, which means that t is infinitely large. So, there is coincidence of the conclusion from both sides.

In Tables I to VI the values of the precipitating concentrations (C) and the times of coagulation with KCl , $BaCl_2$ and $AlCl_3$ have been recorded for Sb_2S_3 and gold sols respectively. By comparing the values of C of these electrolytes, it will be seen that these are in accordance with the Schulze-Hardy law.

The value of ' a ' which has been defined as the critical stability concentration of the electrolyte for the sol remains the same for varying concentrations of the electrolyte. This had also been observed in the slow coagulation of As_2S_3 , $Cr(OH)_3$, $Fe(OH)_3$, Prussian blue and copper ferrocyanide by Bhattacharya *et al.*¹³. The values of a for the mono, bi, and trivalent precipitating ions are also in accordance with the Schulze and Hardy rule, and the values obtained by the visual and extinction techniques are very close to each other for the same electrolyte.

The values of m are in the decreasing order with the increasing valency of the precipitating ions; ' n ', which has been connected with the sensitivity or susceptibility of the sol to the electrolyte, is, however, a very complicated factor in this equation. The numerical values of ' n ' which have been assumed to be a function of the sensitivity of the sol to a particular electrolyte are found to decrease with the increasing valency of the precipitating ion. Since the parameter ' n ' depends on unknown factors, it requires greater elaboration of the conditions to explain the experimental results. Further work is in progress.